

it was felt that the anthocyanidins were not just being produced *in toto* at the required instant. Certain colorless chromogens were already there and a small chemical change was needed for the formation of anthocyanidins. In an earlier paper¹ was discussed the original theory that anthoxanthins (flavonol group, VI) gave rise to anthocyanins (VII) and how it was found to be unsatisfactory. Robinson's later suggestion that both these (VI and VII) arose from a common precursor (IV) was more acceptable.

The discovery of leucoanthocyanidins and the readiness with which they could undergo change into coloured anthocyanidins gave more substance to this idea. The constitutions of leucoanthocyanidins as flavan-3,4-diols (V) are now definite and these are closely related in structure to the hypothetical precursor (IV) which Robinson postulated. Leucoanthocyanidins cannot readily be oxidised to flavonols (VI) except in very special cases, but the change into anthocyanidins is fairly easy. Even here in the laboratory process, which involves boiling with alcoholic hydrochloric acid, the yields never exceed 25%, a considerable amount of a by-product known as phlobaphene being formed. The transformation could be visualised as taking place in two stages: (i) dehydration and (ii) oxidation (see formulae V, VII, and VIII). The first reaction will render the second more easy. It is possible that in the laboratory process, mentioned above, the dehydration is not easy or side reactions are facile. Dehydration, however, can be effectively carried out first by preliminary treatment of a leucoanthocyanidin with hot acetic anhydride, the product being an enol acetate (VIII). By subsequent boiling with alcoholic hydrochloric acid oxidation occurs satisfactorily to give rise to a much higher yield of the anthocyanidin. It seems to be possible that in the plant there is an efficient mechanism for carrying out these two stages in the particular order.

A somewhat similar course seems to be followed in the laboratory method of reductive acetylation applicable to flavonols whereby anthocyanidins are obtained. Taking quercetin (VI) as an example of a readily available flavonol, it is boiled with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate with the addition of zinc powder when it undergoes change into a colorless intermediate acetate which gives rise to a good yield of cyanidin chloride (VII) on acid hydrolysis. The course of this reaction seems to be fairly clear and is indicated by the following formulae. It provides a convenient laboratory method for the preparation of anthocyanidins and the intermediate (VIII) is the same as that shown as the first stage in the above scheme of conversion of leucoanthocyanidins.

At this stage it seemed to be fairly definite that leucoanthocyanidins were the required chromogens for anthocyanidin formation in plants. As a result of considerable study in the group of plant flavonoids, it has been possible to trace the sequence of biosynthesis from the two parts, C_6 and C_9 , originally proposed by Robinson and more recently supported by using radio-tracer technique. The stages concerned with our subject may be indicated by (i) 2'-hydroxychalcone (IX), (ii) flavanone (X), (iii) 3-hydroxyflavanone (XI), and (iv) flavan-3,4-diol (V). The validity of these stages and the importance of 3-hydroxyflavanones as intermediates in biosynthesis were emphasised at the Lyons International Symposium² on oxygen heterocyclic compounds. Further, the easiest method of preparing leucoanthocyanidins is to reduce 3-hydroxyflavanones; for example, taxifolin yields leucocyanidin by reduction. The possibility of this reaction is further supported by the co-occurrence of these two groups of substances in plant sources. The leucoanthocyanidins then undergo a stage of oxidation to give anthocyanidins which are in the same level of oxidation as the original 3-hydroxyflavanones. Thus there is a step down first and then a step up in this scheme of biogenesis.

The significant point to consider now is that the 3-hydroxyflavanones are also colorless compounds. Is it absolutely necessary for them to undergo reduction followed by reoxidation in order to reach the stage of anthocyanidins? Can there be a direct transformation? It looked as if this was possible. Recent experiments studying the behaviour of 3-hydroxyflavanones under various conditions have provided the required clue. If a typical

2. T. R. Seshadri, "Les Heterocycles oxygenes", p. 71, Colloques Internationaux du centre National la Recherche Scientifique, 1965.

3-hydroxyflavanone like taxifolin (XI, R=H) is boiled with acetic anhydride in the presence of a base catalyst like sodium acetate or pyridine, it undergoes complete transformation

into the acetate of cyanidin ψ -base (XIII, R=OAc) which, when deacetylated under mild conditions, gives rise to good yields of cyanidin. The reaction essentially involves an isomeric change pictured in the series of formulae (XI $\rightarrow$ XII $\rightarrow$ XIII; R=H). The first step would be the formation of an enol acetate (XII) followed by a prototropic change of the allylic system. The last step is the familiar ψ -base undergoing change into anthocyanidin. Working with taxifolin itself the intermediate enol acetate could not be isolated, only the ψ -base acetate could be obtained. But if taxifolin tetramethyl ether (XI, R=CH₃)

is used the formation of (i) the normal acetate, (ii) the enol acetate, and (iii) the ψ -base acetate could be definitely established. These points give full support to the mechanism of the isomeric change.

All that has been said above relates to the evolution of the pelargonidin group of anthocyanidins. Members of the gesneridin group could similarly be considered to arise from simpler flavanones in two ways as shown below. The exact conditions necessary to bring about the direct transformation (isomeric change) in the laboratory are not yet known. However, the alternative biosynthetic route can be followed in the laboratory, i.e., the reduction of a flavanone (XIV) to flavan-4-ol (XV) which is conveniently effected by means of sodium borohydride. Subsequent boiling with alcoholic hydrochloric acid gives the corresponding flavylum salt (II) though in a comparatively poor yield. Analogous to this is the easy preparation from flavones (XVI) by reductive acetylation, the immediate products being mainly flavenes (XVII). They undergo deacetylation and oxidation during the boiling with alcoholic hydrochloric acid to give the corresponding flavylum salts in good yields.

Summing up, the present position regarding the origin of anthocyanins could be stated as follows. Colorless 3-hydroxyflavanones can give rise to anthocyanidins of the pelargonidin group in two ways: (i) by direct isomeric change, (ii) by the two-stage conversion involving colorless leucoanthocyanidins as the intermediates. Both these ways can be adopted successfully in the laboratory. Similarly, two processes can be suggested for the biogenesis of the gesneridin type from flavanones without the 3-hydroxyl group, though only the two-stage process is successful in the laboratory.

Regarding the formation of glycosides in plant products, the general opinion is that addition of sugar units to aglycone moieties takes place as a late stage. This does not seem to be altogether correct since in some cases they appear to have entered earlier³. But the above mentioned steps in the biogenesis of the anthocyanins will be valid even if the sugar units were there in an earlier stage. Actually flavonol glycosides can be converted into anthocyanidin glycosides by adopting the method of reductive acetylation.